

(Table 1 contd.)

R = <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl			
9.	C ₆ H ₅	50	118-19
10.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	50	115
11.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	50	125
12.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	54	96
13.	3 Pyridyl	51	85
14.	2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	55	89
15.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	60	100
R = <i>p</i> -Methylphenyl			
17.	C ₆ H ₅	41	159-60
18.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	40	81-82
19.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	39	136
20.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	68	170
21.	2-Furyl	50	181
22.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	40	97
23.	<i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ -N-C ₆ H ₄	43	127
R = 2-Furyl			
24.	C ₆ H ₅	38	104
25.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	42	142
26.	2-Furyl	49	140
27.	2-Pyridyl	37	159
28.	4-Pyridyl	40	157d
29.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	41	129
30.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	40	87
R = 2-Chlorophenyl			
31.	C ₆ H ₅	50	129d
32.	<i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ -N-C ₆ H ₄	30	123
33.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	30	95
34.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	45	85
35.	2-Furyl	40	183d
36.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	50	167
37.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	30	91
R = 4-Chlorophenyl			
38.	2-Pyridyl	30	220
39.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₅	35	155
40.	2-Thionyl	35	160
41.	C ₆ H ₅	39	124
42.	2-Furyl	30	190
43.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	42	225
44.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	42	150

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

aroyl-3-arylacrylophenones (1) with *o*-phenylenediamine (2) in boiling ethanolic medium in presence of a little glacial acetic acid (Scheme 1).

Scheme_1

Experimental

The 2'-hydroxy-2-aroyl-3-arylacrylophenones (1) were prepared by the known procedure³.

3-Benzylidene-2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-4-phenyl-1,5-benzodiazepine (3). Typical procedure: A mixture of 2'-hydroxy-2-benzoyl-3-phenylacrylophenone (2 g), *o*-phenylenediamine (0.64 g), ethanol (25 ml) and glacial acetic acid (0.5 ml) was refluxed for 12 h. The solvent was then removed and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (56%), m.p. 128° (Found: C, 83.8; H, 4.9; N, 6.9. C₂₈H₂₀N₂O requires: C, 84.0; H, 5.0; N, 7.0%); its alcoholic solution gave a violet colouration with concentrated HCl indicating the diazepine structure; $\nu_{\max}$ 1590 (C=N), 1340 (C-N) and 1650 cm⁻¹ (C=C).

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Synthesis and Biological Studies of some Imidazolones

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IMIDAZOLONES show diverse biological properties¹. We report here the synthesis and biological activities of some imidazolones² (1) obtained by the condensation of 2-phenyl-4-(4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxybenzylidene)oxazol-5-one with sulphonamides. The imidazolones (1a-j; Table 1) showed appropriate uv and ir spectral data.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE IMIDAZOLONES (1a–j)*

Compd. no.	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	Colour	$\lambda_{\max}$ (nm)
1a	H	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅ S	180	50	Brown	212, 256, 203
b	Guanidinyl	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₅ S	142	57	Yellow	217, 327, 383
c	2'-Pyrimidinyl	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₅ S	122	70	Yellow	211, 283
d	2',6'-Dimethoxy-4'-pyrimidinyl	C ₂₉ H ₂₅ N ₅ O ₇ S	150	66	Dark yellow	211, 276
e	1'-Phenylpyrazole-5'-yl	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₅ S	106	80	Dark brown	215, 382
f	5'-Methyl-1',3',4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₅ S ₂	109	47	Light yellow	214, 280, 306, 430
g	2',6'-Dimethyl-4'-pyrimidinyl	C ₂₈ H ₂₅ N ₅ O ₅ S	140	50	Yellow	211, 282, 386
h	4',6'-Dimethyl-2'-pyrimidinyl	C ₂₉ H ₂₅ N ₅ O ₅ S	121	45	Light yellow	217, 269, 373
i	4'-Methyl-2'-pyrimidinyl	C ₂₈ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₅ S	130	64	Yellow	211, 264, 330
j	2'-Thiazolyl	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₅ S ₂	160	72	Light yellow	208, 288, 382

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 435 spectrophotometer and uv spectra (isopropanol) on a Shimadzu 160 spectrophotometer.

2-Phenyl-4-(4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxybenzylidene)-oxazole-5-one: The compound was synthesised using the reported procedure³.

1-(Substituted-sulphamidophenyl)-2-phenyl-4-(4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxybenzylidene)-5-imidazolone (1). *General method of preparation:* A mixture of the above oxazol-5-one (0.02 mol) and sulphonamide (0.02 mol) was refluxed in pyridine (20 ml) for 5 h. Excess pyridine was then distilled off and to the residue was added concentrated HCl (10 ml) and crushed ice, and the mixture was left overnight.

The resulting solid (1a–j) was washed with water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol.

The imidazolones showed expected ir absorption frequencies for NH str. (3 200 cm⁻¹ for 1e and 3 300 for the rest), C=O str. (1 700 for 1i, 1 750 for 1a, 1e, 1j and 1 760 for the rest), C=N str. (1 620 for 1b, 1 630 for 1a, 1 690 for 1c, 1g and 1h, and 1 640 for the rest and asymmetric and symmetric SO₂ str. (1 360/1 370 and 1 130–1 150 cm⁻¹, respectively).

Biological screening: Antimicrobial screening of the compounds was done *in vitro* against five bacteria *Streptococcus faecalis*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus* as well as five fungi *Candida albicans*, *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Sporothrichum schenkii*, *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* and *Aspergillus fumigatus*, using the reported method⁴. Compounds 1b and 1g were found active against *T. mentagrophytes* (MIC being 25 µg ml⁻¹). The maximum concentration of all the compounds tested was 100 µg ml⁻¹.

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Studies on 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Aryl-5-(5',7'-diiodo-8'-quinolinoxy)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles

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1,3,4-Oxadiazole derivatives possess diverse biological activities and there are numerous reports that highlight their chemistry and use¹. With a view to getting newer oxadiazoles with better therapeutic activity we have synthesised compounds 4 bearing 5,7-diiodo-8-hydroxyquinolinyl moiety.

5,7-Diiodo-8-hydroxyquinoline (1) was condensed with ethyl chloroformate to get ethyl (5,7-diiodoquinolin-8-yl-oxy) formate (2), which was further treated with hydrazine hydrate to obtain the corresponding hydrazide (3). It was then condensed with different aromatic acids in presence of phosphorous oxychloride to yield various 1,3,4-oxadiazoles (4). The structures of the products have been characterised by elemental analyses and ir spectral study. The compounds were screened for their antimicrobial activity.

Antimicrobial activity: The compounds were screened for antibacterial and antifungal activity using cup-plate method². The testing was carried out at a concentration of 100 μg using gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and *S. citreus*, gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* and *Mercsane serratia* and fungi *Aspergillus niger* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. Most of the compounds were found moderately active (13–24 mm zone of inhibition) against the aforesaid strains of bacteria and fungi.

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) were taken on a Shimadzu DR-1, 435 spectrophotometer.

5,7-Diiodoquinolin-8-oxynoylhydrazide (3): A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol, 4.69 g) in dioxane (35 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol, 1.04 g) was refluxed at 100–02° for 3 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (80.0%), m.p. 201–03° (Found : C, 26.32; H, 1.50; N, 9.20. C₁₀H₇I₂N₃O₂ calcd. for : C, 26.37; H, 1.53; N, 9.23%); ν_{max} 3 400 (NH), 1 680 (C=O), 770 (NH wag) and 630 cm⁻¹ (C–I).

Preparation of 4: Benzoic acid (0.05 mol, 0.61 g) was refluxed with the hydrazide (3; 0.05 mol, 2.28 g) in presence of phosphorus oxychloride (0.05 mol) for 5 h. The contents were then poured into water and basified with sodium bicarbonate solution. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (Ar=Ph; 60.0%), m.p. 173° (Found : C, 37.62; H, 1.62; N, 7.72. C₁₇H₉I₂N₃O₂ calcd. for : C, 37.70; H, 1.66; N, 7.76%); ν_{max} 1 590 (C=N), 1 130 (C–O–C), 1 040 (N–N) and 650 cm⁻¹ (C–I).

Similarly, other substituted oxadiazoles were prepared (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE OXADIAZOLES (4)

Sl. no.	Ar	Mol. formula	M.p. °C
1.	Phenyl	C ₁₇ H ₉ I ₂ N ₃ O ₂	173
2.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₇ H ₈ ClI ₂ N ₃ O ₂	224
3.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₇ H ₈ ClI ₂ N ₃ O ₂	218
4.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₇ H ₈ ClI ₂ N ₃ O ₂	202
5.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₇ H ₉ I ₂ N ₃ O ₃	280
6.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₇ H ₉ I ₂ N ₃ O ₃	208
7.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₇ H ₉ I ₂ N ₃ O ₃	255
8.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₁₇ H ₈ I ₂ N ₄ O ₄	258
9.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₁₇ H ₈ I ₂ N ₄ O ₄	195
10.	<i>o</i> -Aminophenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ I ₂ N ₄ O ₂	189
11.	<i>m</i> -Aminophenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ I ₂ N ₄ O ₂	231
12.	<i>p</i> -Aminophenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ I ₂ N ₄ O ₂	256
13.	2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl	C ₁₇ H ₉ I ₂ N ₃ O ₄	170
14.	2,6-Dihydroxyphenyl	C ₁₇ H ₉ I ₂ N ₃ O ₄	184
15.	Cinnamyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ I ₂ N ₃ O ₂	220
16.	<i>p</i> -Pyridyl	C ₁₇ H ₉ I ₂ N ₄ O ₂	235
17.	<i>o</i> -Acetoxyphenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ I ₂ N ₃ O ₄	247
18.	3,4,5-Trihydroxyphenyl	C ₁₇ H ₉ I ₂ N ₃ O ₆	188

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